

Kinetics of the Hofmann Bromoamide Reaction

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N-Bromoamides corresponding to acet-, propion-, and isobutyramides have been prepared and the rate of liberation of bromide ion from these compounds has been investigated. The reaction is of first order with respect to the bromoamide and is catalysed by hydroxyl ions. The rate is found to increase considerably for higher amide derivatives. Energy of activation, autocatalytic effect of OH⁻ ions, etc. have been investigated. A mechanism for the Hofmann reaction is suggested on the basis of the decomposition of the bromoamide ion being dependent on the ease of rearrangement.

The Hofmann bromoamide reaction¹ involves the conversion of an amide to an amine containing one less carbon atom. The generally accepted mechanism² of the reaction is

Hofmann³ reported the formation of intermediate bromoamide as also of the isocyanate. Kinetic study of the bromoamide decomposition was made by Hauser and Renfrow⁴ on the substituted *N*-bromobenzamides and the reaction was shown to be of first order with respect to bromoamide. As the kinetic data on the decomposition of aliphatic bromoamides are not available in the literature, the kinetic study of the decomposition of acet-, propion-, and butyr-bromoamides has been undertaken with a view to ascertaining the mechanism of the Hofmann reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. R. acetamide was purified according to the standard procedure⁵ by crystallising from methanol solutions to which a small quantity of ether was added. The crystals were washed with chilled ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Propionamide, *n*-butyramide, and isobutyramide were prepared, according to the method reported by Vogel⁶, from the acid and urea distillation. The amides were purified by distillation, the fraction being collected near the boiling point of the amide. The molecular weight of the amide was checked by depression of freezing point of water. All other reagents used were of A.R. quality. The solutions were made in double-distilled water.

N-Bromoamide.—To a chilled solution (1:1) of the amide and bromide KOH solution was added till the colour was pale yellow and then the mixture left for 3-4 hr. After adding

1. *Ber.*, 1861, 14, 2725; 1862, 15, 407.

2. Wallis and Lane, "Organic Reactions", Vol. III, p. 268, John Wiley & Son, 1947.

3. *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2754.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 121.

5. Wagher, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1930, 7, 1135.

6. "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 403.

pure sodium chloride, it was extracted with hot chloroform. The bromoamide was precipitated by adding *n*-hexane. The precipitate was removed by filtration, washed with dry hexane, and dried by suction. The purity of the sample was determined by iodimetric titration. The m.p. and purity of the samples are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

	M.P.	%Purity.
<i>N</i> -Bromoacetamide (BAA)	102-103°	98.2
<i>N</i> -Bromopropionamide (BPA)	79-80.5°	87.6
<i>N</i> -Bromoisobutyramide (BIBA)	80-81.0°	98.5

Incidentally, it was not possible to isolate the corresponding compound of *n*-butyramide. The procedure recorded above yielded a yellow compound, rapidly losing bromine, leaving a white solid melting at 102.4°. Estimation of C, H and N in this compound and of the molecular weight showed the compound to be

Kinetic Study.—For the kinetic study, the bromoamides were always freshly prepared as these evolved bromine on exposure to light. Kinetic runs were done in the usual manner, removing 5-ml aliquots from the reaction vessel, kept in a thermostat with a temperature regulation of $\pm 0.05^\circ$ and titrated against a standard thiosulphate solution.

TABLE II

Temp. = 30°. KOH = 0.25*N*.

	Conc. of BA in mixture.	k_{uni}^{30}
a.	0.025 <i>N</i> BAA	$1.35 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$
b.	0.025 <i>N</i> BPA	1.80×10^{-4}
c.	0.025 <i>N</i> BIBA	0.37×10^{-4}

DISCUSSION

Table II records the results of experiments carried out to determine the rate of decomposition of *N*-bromoamides (BA) in excess of KOH. The reaction is unimolecular with respect to the BA.

The rate thus is seen to be the smallest for the BAA. As a matter of fact, the failure to obtain the corresponding bromine compound of *n*-butyramide can be attributed to a very fast rate of decomposition in presence of a slight excess of KOH used to isolate this compound.

Table III records the effect of temperature on the unimolecular reaction-rate constant. The energy of activation (*E*) and frequency factor (*A*) are calculated using the Arrhenius expression.

TABLE III

	Temp.	K_{uni} (min.)	k (mole mol^{-1})	A (min.) at 30°
1. BAA	30°	1.35×10^{-4}	47800	2.1×10^{10}
	40°	2.3×10^{-3}		
	50°	1.37×10^{-2}		
2. BPA	30°	1.86×10^{-2}	26200	1.2×10^{17}
	40°	9.3×10^{-2}		
	50°	2.9×10^{-1}		
3. BIBA	10°	1.0×10^{-2}	27300	1.4×10^{10}
	20°	1.0×10^{-1}		
	30°	3.7×10^{-1}		

The results in Table III show a very large energy of activation as also frequency factor for BAA, but for higher amides these values are considerably low. Reaction-rate constants, using equivalent quantities of BA and KOH, were determined over a concentration range of 0.073*N* to 0.245*N* of the salt. The value for K_{uni} was found to be $8.8 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-5}$ min. at 50°. The results thus show that the BA anion decomposes with a unimolecular mechanism in absence of OH⁻ ions. The influence of OH⁻ is therefore considered catalytic. Apparently, the rate constant does not change appreciably with increasing ionic strength of the solution; this follows from the fact that the decomposition is a first-order ionic reaction. The influence of KOH on the reaction rate is brought out in Table IV.

TABLE IV

BAA = 0.04 *N*

Conc. of free OH ⁻ in soln.	..	0.00	0.08	0.16	0.28
K_{uni}^{50} (min.)	..	9.6×10^{-3}	1.1×10^{-2}	1.2×10^{-2}	1.4×10^{-2}

Plotting free OH⁻ ion concentration against K_{obs} , a straight line was obtained obeying.

$$K_{\text{obs}} = 9.6 \times 10^{-3} + 0.022 C_{\text{OH}^-}$$

From the data presented above, we conclude that *N*-BA decomposition is a first-order reaction and is catalysed by OH⁻ ions. Conductance measurements have shown that the BA's are weak acids. Hence the possible steps in the reaction can be

In excess of KOH, the free acid is completely converted to the salt and the anion releases the Br⁻ ion according to reaction (2). The kinetic expression for the catalysed reaction can be written as

$$-\frac{d(\text{BA}^-)}{dt} = K_1 (\text{BA}^-) + K_1 (\text{BA}^-) (\text{OH}^-)$$

since $K_{\text{obs}} = K_0 + K_1 [\text{OH}^-]$. The curious feature of this reaction is very high energy of activation and decrease in the rate with the higher amides. Pertinently, the energy of activation for BPA and BIBA is very nearly the same, whereas for BAA it is considerably higher. It is interesting to determine the contribution by the reactivities of the BA's in question to the total free energy of activation by heat and entropy effects. Using Eyring's equation:

$$K_r = \frac{KT}{h} e^{-\frac{\Delta^\ddagger H}{RT}} \cdot e^{-\frac{\Delta^\ddagger S}{RT}}$$

and equating $\Delta^\ddagger H$ with the experimental energy of activation⁸, the value of $\Delta^\ddagger S$ can be calculated in the case of first-order reactions.

TABLE V

Temp. = 30°

	$\Delta^\ddagger H$	$\Delta^\ddagger S$
BAA	47.8 kcal.	71.7 e.u.
BPA	26.2	34.8
BIBA	27.3	23.7

The values of $\Delta^\ddagger S$ are seen to be positive. Such a positive entropy effect has already been noted for the first-order alkaline hydrolysis of α -bromopropionate ion by Chadwick and Pecsú⁹ and by Lam and Heine⁸ in their study on the alkaline hydrolysis of bromo-acid anion. This has been interpreted as due to the freeing of water molecules "frozen" round the anion as the activated state is reached. This appears to be a plausible explanation of the positive entropy change observed, the 'melting' occurring as the rearrangement takes place within the molecule. The reaction therefore seems to consist of the rearrangement taking place as the bromide ion gets out, thus

The transfer of R^- from the carboxylic carbon to the nitrogen will obviously be facilitated by the greater chain length in R, which can approach more closely to the nitrogen group by bending. It is therefore not surprising that the rate of removal of Br^- , which depends on the ease of migration of R^- , is smallest in acetamide.

7. Frost and Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", pp. 100, John Wiley & Son, 1953.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 392.

9. *Ibid.*, 1951, 73, 1349.